

1 **Growth factor signaling in IBD.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We used next-generation sequencing to characterize growth factor signaling dynamics in humans with the
8 inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) Crohn's Disease. A number of gene products functioning in transduction
9 of growth factor signals were found to be activated in the whole blood in humans with CD during periods of
10 active disease. Grb10, Pdgfc, Fgf13 and Igfbp2 were among the most highly enriched gene products in
11 the peripheral blood of humans with Crohn's Disease during acute disease exacerbation. In a separate
12 manuscript, we describe alterations in the hepatocyte growth factor HGF-MET signaling pathway in
13 humans with CD.

14 Citations

15 1. Griga, T., Tromm, A., Spranger, J. and May, B., 1998. Increased serum levels of vascular
16 endothelial growth factor in patients with inflammatory bowel disease. Scandinavian journal of
17 gastroenterology, 33(5), pp.504-508.

18 2. Stakenborg, M., Verstockt, B., Meroni, E., Goverse, G., De Simone, V., Verstockt, S., Di Matteo,
19 M., Czarnewski, P., Villablanca, E.J., Ferrante, M. and Boeckxstaens, G.E., 2020. Neutrophilic HGF-MET
20 signalling exacerbates intestinal inflammation. Journal of Crohn's and Colitis, 14(12), pp.1748-1758.

21 3. Srivastava, M., Zurakowski, D., Cheifetz, P., Leichtner, A. and Bousvaros, A., 2001. Elevated
22 serum hepatocyte growth factor in children and young adults with inflammatory bowel disease. Journal of
23 pediatric gastroenterology and nutrition, 33(5), pp.548-553.

24 4. Tahara, Y., Ido, A., Yamamoto, S., Miyata, Y., Uto, H., Hori, T., Hayashi, K. and Tsubouchi, H.,
25 2003. Hepatocyte growth factor facilitates colonic mucosal repair in experimental ulcerative colitis in rats.
26 The Journal of pharmacology and experimental therapeutics, 307(1), pp.146-151.

27 5. Beck, P.L. and Podolsky, D.K., 1999. Growth factors in inflammatory bowel disease. Inflammatory
28 bowel diseases, 5(1), pp.44-60.

GSE186507